

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE CITIZEN'S MEETINGS OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD OF KARSHI CITY

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Annotation: This article describes the activities of the chairmen and deputy chairmen of the existing neighborhoods in Karshi, as well as the issues of providing social services in the neighborhoods and raising the service of helping families in need of social protection to a new level, and further accelerating the work of training women for professions.

Key words: Organazation of self-government of citizens, prevention inspector, neighborhood, Citizens' meetings, Independence, Navo, Navroz, Nasaf, entrepreneurship, landowners.

As of April 1, 2015, there were 62 neighborhoods in the city of Karshi, the total number of residents was 277,904, the total number of families was 61,796, the number of low-income families was 1,529, and the total number of households was 47,664.

In 2012-2015, 14 of the existing 62 neighborhoods were considered exemplary Organazation of self-government of citizens.

44 of the existing 62 neighborhoods in the city of Karshi[1] are located in the buildings that are included in the balance sheet, 18 are non-listed Organazation of self-government of citizens, and the number of OSGC located in the same building with the prevention inspector is 12 , the number of counseling centers was 62.

The number of Organazations of self-government of citizens provided with a computer set[2:1492-1495] was 29, and the number of them that needed to be provided with new mobile equipment was 33.

In the elections of Organazation of self-government of citizens chairmen held in 2019, 8 out of 62 neighborhoods were dismissed from the Organazation of self-government of citizens chair after the election, of which 5 according to their application, 2 due to health, 1 4 chairpersons were re-elected as one moved to another job.

The order of the Republican Council on Coordination of the Activities of Citizens' Self-Management Bodies[3:135-138] dated July 18, 2017 "Rating the efficiency of the work of citizens' assembly workers[4:1-6] and activists" On the basis of the regulation approved by the statement No. 2 "On the activities" at the end of 2019, according to the results of the rating evaluation of the efficiency of the work of the

employees and activists of the citizens' meetings, the activities of the existing 62 neighborhoods in the city of Karshi [5:96-100] are "exemplary" (71-100 points) – A.Navoi, Arabkhana, Aralovul, Bogishamol, Boston, Buyuk Turan, Gafur Ghulam, Gulshan, Zahokimaron, Zogza, Komandi, Qarliqbogot, Qarliqkhana, Karshi, Kat, Qilichbek Kurgancha, Kurgancha, Maghan, Mahallot, Maksimabad, Independence, Navo, Navro'z, Nasaf, Oktepa, Pakhtazar, Ravak, Roguzar, Samarkand, Temiryolchi, Kharamjoi, Khontep, Shaikhali, Shokhbekat, Shortangaz (total 35), the activity is "good" evaluated citizens' assemblies (up to 51-70 points) - Amir Temur, Aral, Batosh, Beglar, Geologist, Darvozatutak, Istiklal, Kunchikar, Nakhlahz [7:128-131], Neftchi, Otchopar, Pakhtazor-1, Khojakhyol, Chakar, Charmgar, Cholkuvar, Shaikhali town (total 17), citizens' gatherings rated as "average" (up to 50 points) - Gungon, Qavali, Kamilon, Nuristan, Aydin, Tabassum, Khudoyzod, Shodlik, Eski Pomegranate, New Marriage (total 10) (rated on 25 criteria).

As of December 23, 2019[8:128-132] the age of the chairpersons of the ANC of the opposite city is 8 30-40-year-olds, 20 40-50-year-olds, 24 50-60-year-olds (including 6 women), over 60 young people made up 10 (including 2 women), according to the information of the chairpersons, 59 of the 62 chairpersons had a higher education, and 3 had a secondary education.

The age and education of the responsible secretaries of citizens' meetings of Karshi city are as follows: 62 (including 49 women), 11(7) under 30, 19(14) 30-40-year-olds, 40-50-year-olds 21(20), 50-60-year-olds 11(8), according to the information of responsible secretaries, 23 have higher education, 39 have secondary special education.

The age and education of the deputy chairman of the citizens' meetings of Karshi city - advisers on youth issues were as follows: 62 (including 11 women), 29(2) under 30, 17 30-40-year-olds. (3), 40-50-year-olds 11(3), 50-60-year-olds 5(3), and according to their education, 12 had a higher education, 48 had a special secondary education, and 2 had a secondary education.

The age and education of the deputy chairman of the citizens' meetings of Karshi city - advisers on the affairs of the elderly and veterans [9:73-76] were as follows. 62 (including 3 women), 44(2) 50-60 year olds, 6(1) over 60 years old, and according to education, 27 of them had higher education, 25 had secondary special education, and 2 had secondary education.

The age[10] and education of the Deputy Chairman of the Citizens' Meetings of Karshi City - Counselors on Spiritual and Educational Issues were as follows. 62(25),

under 30 1(1), 30-40-year-old 6(3), 40-50-year-old 22(10), 50-60-year-old 16(7), over 60 17(4)), 40 with higher education, 22 with secondary specialized education.

The age and education of the deputy chairman of the citizens' meetings of the city of Karshi - support for the activities of entrepreneurship, homestead landowners [11:59-63] and beautification works were as follows. 62 (25 women), 11(2) under 30, 25(11) 30-40-year-olds, 12(6) 40-50-year-olds, 10(4) 50-60-year-olds, 4 over 60 (2) made up 31 higher education, 25 secondary education, 6 secondary education.

Crimes committed by employees working in the citizens' assembly of the opposite city[12:86-90] 1 "Beglar" assembly of neighborhood citizens (ANC) chairman Arabova Bakharoy Kholmominovna for committing the crime provided for in Article 210, Part 2, Clause v of the Civil Code found guilty and brought to justice.

District on ensuring the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2022 "On additional measures to increase the employment of women [13:386-391] and strengthen their health" Establishment of women's employment and health promotion centers in the neighborhoods of (city)s.

In order to ensure the implementation of this decision, the center for ensuring the employment and health promotion of women has started working at the "Ravak" ANC in Karshi.

The Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Zulayho Mahkamova, the head of the Regional Department of Family and Women Komila Karomova got acquainted with the activity of the center[2].

A meeting was held with members of the regional "Smart Women" movement and family women's problem at the "Ishga Marhamat" monocenter in the city of Karshi. Komila Karomova, the deputy governor of the region, spoke at the event and said that each of the 1,718,737 women in the region is always under consideration.

On June 29, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise the provision of social services in neighborhoods and help families in need of social protection to a new level, and to further accelerate the work of training women for professions" The work carried out in Kashkadarya region was analyzed in connection with the implementation of the decision. Y. Ergasheva, the chairman of Vtloyat Olima women's association, G. Uzokova, head of the regional "Aqila women" movement, were heard. Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Zulayho Mahkamova spoke at the event.

- Continuous monitoring of the timely and quality provision of social services in the process of studying the work carried out for women and girls in our country,

studying the condition of each household, determining the real situation of families and their need for social services, studying the implementation of the social protection plan - Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Zulayho Mahkamova said.

If a girl has a higher education, the more knowledge she acquires, she will pass it on to her children in the future. Therefore, each of us is responsible for this. Exhibition of inventions of women scientists and products made by women artisan entrepreneurs in our region was organized in the monocenter.

As of January 1, 2022, there are 62 neighborhoods in the city of Karshi, 1 town assembly, 61 neighborhood assemblies, 3 with a population of 1,000-2,000, and 2,000-4,000. 29 with a population of 4,000-6,000, 23 with a population of 6,000-8,000, 2 with a population of 8,000-10,000, and 2 with a population of 10,000-12,000 2 of them, and 2 of those with a population of more than 12,000 people. According to the number of families, 33 ANCs have families up to 1,000, and 29 have families from 1,000 to 2,000. The number of ANCs with the number of households up to 1000 is 36, the number of ANCs with the number of households from 1000 to 2000 is 24, and the number of ANCs with the number of households from 2001 to 3000 is 2.

There are 7 deputies of the chairman of the citizens' meetings of Karshi city for family, women's and social, spiritual [14:292-296] issues from 30 to 40 years old, 45 from 40 to 60 years old, and those over 60 years old. 10, 30 with higher education, and 31 with secondary specialized education.

53 out of 61 deputies of the chairman of citizens' gatherings on improvement, real estate and business issues [15:26-28] are women, 7 are under 30 years old, 13 are 30-40 years old, 40 to 60 years old 40, 1 over 60 years old, 12 with higher education, 46 with special secondary education, 3 with secondary education. The number of deputy chairmen who resigned in 2022 was 1 person.

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